

The Pandemic's Repercussions: Tales of Filipino Teachers Working in American Schools Amidst COVID-19

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Abstract. This study explored the experiences, struggles, coping mechanisms, and insights of Filipino teachers working in the United States of America amidst the pandemic. The participants were coming from the primary schools of Carlsbad which is a city in and the county seat of Eddy County, New Mexico, United States. There were six (6) teachers who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas from the participants. The participants were purposely selected as representatives from the group of Filipino teachers who are assigned to different grade levels but in the same district. The virtual in-depth interview was employed to gather significant information with regard to their respective lived experiences. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged pertaining to their lived experiences: Learning through Technology, Technological Stress, More Challenged Teachers and Enhancing Online Educational Practices. There were three subthemes that emerged on the challenges experienced by the participants. These are Intermittent Internet Connections, Lack of physical activity and interactions and Language Barriers Online. The coping mechanisms of teacher participants on the challenges they experienced were: Considering professional development and Valuing Resilience and Change Management. The educational management insights drawn from the participants were the Value of Social Connectedness and the importance of adaptation for survival. Thus, the educational institutions where Filipino teachers may be employed may assign senior teachers with valuable support networks to employed foreign or Filipino teachers. This support can be provided in a variety of ways, such as through training programs or mentoring relationships that include academic, technological, cultural, and institutional-specific information.

KEY WORDS

1. lived experiences 2. pandemic 3. distance learning

Date Received: September 05, 2024 — Date Reviewed: September 10, 2024 — Date Published: October 10, 2024

1. Introduction

The past year has been unprecedented in recent history, and the year 2020 has brought about a great deal of economic unpredictability for schools as well as for their employees. The occurrence of COVID-19 pandemic has had a fundamental impact on practically every aspect of life, including education, and Filipino teachers' conditions wherever country they are in have not been an exception to this norm. The strain and increased pressure that was placed on educators during the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the educators' fears regarding the fu-

ture of their employment, were exposed. The complications and problems that the pandemic has produced within the training framework of teachers must also be managed and fought by them. The peak of the illness is still unpredicted at the present time, and teachers are continuously feeling the pressure that this produces; in effect, they are still going through a worldwide pandemic laterally with everyone else in the world. Along with their struggles being away from home are the pandemic-related obstacles that doubled their feelings of stress, uncertainties and tribulations. Globally, the COVID 19 pandemic has produced a problem that has affected every school individual, and school closures as part of steps to stop the spread of the virus have presented challenges that have altered the face of education throughout the world (Korkmaz Mirici, 2021). In Germany, as a result of the pandemic-caused shift, nearly nine out of ten educators feel very uncomfortable and stressed. In addition, the poll indicated that 81% of teachers in the United States of America, since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, the teaching profession has undergone a continuous change. AdoptAClassroom.org (2022) surveyed teachers around the nation in March, two years into the pandemic, in order to better comprehend the present state of education. In 2022, the state of teaching in the U.S was hampered by the effects of the pandemic where 81% of teachers workloads have increased, 80% more time is needed to address students and teachers mental health needs, 69% of learning loss, and 55% less planning time due to shortage of school staff and other factors. These add pressure and stress

to Filipino teachers working in different states being frontliners of schools in the new normal. Filipino teachers have suffered with their personal and professional lives. The majority of Filipino teachers are afflicted by this issue and have encountered no-work, no-pay situations, although some are engaged through agencies. In order to survive in the teaching profession in this new normal context, their struggle for survival in a foreign country is real. Filipino teachers' conceptions of the nature of successful teaching include personality-based characteristic dispositions and teaching competence-based dispositions that are deeply entrenched in Filipino cultural values and ideals (Bustos-Orosa, 2008). As a researcher who is also working in one of the public schools of New Mexico, USA., I believe that it is crucial to explore the lived experiences of other Filipino Teachers working abroad amidst the pandemic. The research gap focuses on the difficulties they encountered as foreign educators amidst the global pandemic. I am particularly motivated to dive into the deeper aspects of their professional experiences where I can also investigate deeper the lessons they gained. In this regard, I examined the personal motivations of Filipino teachers as well as their efforts to show their worth as professionals and achieve their life goals. I am also especially interested in how the Filipino educators overcame the difficulties brought on by the COVID 19 pandemic. Their experiences may be termed a phenomenon and could best serve as an inspiration for other Filipino teachers to bring out their best in terms of their profession.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study is to ascertain or explore the lived experiences of Filipino teachers teaching in American Schools specifically in the State of New Mexico. This is a qualitative research endeavor that focuses on the participants' viewpoints on the widespread occurrence of difficulties among teachers working abroad amidst the pandemic. As a constructivist researcher, I am interested in the individual realities and professional identities of the participants, as well as the implications of these constructions for their work as educators. Hence, the purpose of the study was to provide thorough descriptions and

narratives that mirrored the participants' interpretations of the phenomena. The most effective educators choose employment that satisfies not just their needs but also their desires and wants that is why teachers chose to stay abroad even if they are faced with uncertainties. Indeed, this is a challenge. Moreover, the lessons learned by the participants may serve as an eye-opener for all those affiliated with local or foreign academic institutions. In addition, given the small number of studies undertaken on Filipino teachers' experiences and perspectives on working abroad amidst the pandemic, this paper will fill in the literature and pave the path for future local, national and even international empirical research. Importantly, the outcomes of this study will inform policymakers, school administrators, and educators as to what they can do to fill the gap in the current studies. Thus, this study is thought to be of great importance.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are the personal and professional experiences of Filipino teachers working in Public American schools amidst the pandemic?
- (2) How do Filipino teachers cope with the challenges they experienced as foreign teachers amidst the pandemic in Public American Schools?
- (3) What are the management insights of Filipino teachers regarding their experiences amidst the pandemic as foreign teachers in Public American Schools?

*1.3. Definition of Terms—*The following terms are operationally defined to make this study more comprehensive. Overseas Filipino Workers (OFW). Operationally, defined as Filipino citizen who is living and working in another country specifically in the study, they are the Filipino teachers working abroad. In the study, they are Filipino teachers working as teachers in the United States of America and are J-1 and HB-1 Visa holders. Pandemic Repercussions. This refers to the changes, widespread, indirect, or unforeseen effect of pandemic in the lives of the Filipino Teachers working in the United States. Teacher Challenges. This is often understood to mean a direct threat to

a school teachers' position due to different factors but specifically, in the study, this focuses on the work-life problems or issues experienced by Filipino teachers working in the U.S amidst the pandemic. CoVid-19 Pandemic. The COVID-19 pandemic is an outbreak of coronavirus that has occurred all over the world. Coronavirus is an infectious disease that is caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) virus. New Normal. An era in education placing a greater emphasis on the use of technological tools in the classroom after the advent of COVID-19. It is widely believed that educational practices in the "new normal" will never again be the same as they were before the pandemic.

*1.4. Significant of the Study—*To clearly determine the outcomes of this study and to whom the findings are addressed, the following persons or agencies were the beneficiaries. Administrators and Supervisors. This study may help DepEd supervisors and administrators create teacher training and seminars to encourage Filipino teachers love their jobs in the

Philippines instead of leaving for abroad. International administrators where Filipino teachers work at present may also create programs to help Filipino teachers overcome their challenges, knowing that teachers perform better when they feel like they belong and are protected in the workplace. Further, this study may be helpful to school administrators or principals

since it considers them to be a factor or reason that may contribute to teachers' attrition or a human element that contributes to instructors leaving their jobs based on the previous readings. It will provide them with the chance to evaluate and reflect on their own experiences regarding the ways in which they interact with other people. Teachers. In terms of deciding whether to continue working as educators in the country or to pursue their plans of going and settling abroad for greener pastures, this study would be a great avenue for those who aspire to become teachers or who would like to work as international teachers. It would help them decide whether to stay as educators working in the country or whether to pursue their plans. In the course of this research, the experiences of participants will be used to provide lessons from which other participants can also benefit or from which they can take into consideration. Students. This study is significant to those students who would like to know and understand

deeper the struggles of Filipino Teachers away from their country. Policy Makers. This study would also be useful to policymakers, particularly those with the power to formulate educational mandates, policy measures, and orders as their guidelines for preserving or even conserving the number of the best teachers in Philippine schools. Or, this may serve as the basis for humanitarian programs that may help alleviate the problems or difficulties encountered by OFWs or Filipino teachers working abroad. Future Researchers. This study provides research literature that could also serve as the basis for future researchers who would wish to conduct a study parallel to the themes of this study and or applying other categories that their study will cover. The study could be a strong basis especially for those who will engage in qualitative research employing phenomenology or in other words, this would serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study is grounded in the transactional model of stress and coping developed by Lazarus and Folkman. This is one of the earliest models created with the intention of describing and explaining the process an individual undergoes when attempting to cope with stressful situations. The model posits that there is an interaction between the individual and the stressful condition, which is most evident in the individual's evaluation of the confronting situation. Lazarus and Folkman (1984) define stress as a unique interaction between the individual and his environment, which is manifested by the individual's perception that the situation he is facing significantly strains or exceeds his mental resources, hence threatening his mental equilibrium. According to the interactive model, the individual undergoes two distinct processes that are crucial to the resolution of the issue. The first is cogni-

tive assessment, which refers to the individual's relationship to the situation and its scope. The second aspect relates to the resolution of the issue. Attempting to find a solution, tolerating and/or reducing the external and internal pressures caused by the situation is the definition of problem resolution. The model is not linear in nature. Lazarus and Folkman (1984) assert, to the contrary, that coping with stress is a dynamic process in which revision of the assessment leads to changes in coping strategies and vice versa. Two distinct phases are identified in the cognitive evaluation procedure. The first stage is the primary evaluation, which occurs when the individual evaluates the significance of the event and assigns it a meaning (i.e. insignificant, positive, emotionally depressing, and so on). The second stage is the secondary evaluation, in which the individual evaluates his or her existing resources for coping with the ex-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

perience (i.e. perception of control of stressful conditions, in other words, to what extent the problem is controllable). This study is also related and connected to Boakaerts’s first review of stress and coping methods (1996). He presented the entire ”stress-coping” procedure as a series of successive elements that interact with one another from the moment a stressful stimulus is encountered until it is resolved. They include (1) the unpleasant situation itself, (2) the coping skills, (3) the goals of coping, (4) the evaluation of the situation, (5) the intention to cope, and (6) the specific coping tactics

employed. This research study of teachers’ experiences with pandemic-related stress in the new normal seeks to identify connections between the aforementioned ideas and to comprehend how stress might alter teachers’ attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors in elementary public schools today. This will also illustrate how educators’ activities are guided and explained by various ideas concerning stress and coping strategies especially when one is disconnected from his usual environment and life companions.

2. Methodology

Presented in this chapter is the method. It includes the Philosophical Assumption, Qualitative Assumption, Design and Procedure, Research, Participants, Role of the Researcher, Data Collection, Data Analysis, and Trustworthiness of the Study.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumptions in my study were used in analyzing and interpreting my results. At its most basic level, psychological research

can be used to explain and forecast parts of the human experience, improve our understanding of the lived experiences of different groups of people, or criticize and change the current

conditions in which we live and seek to grow (Lincoln, Lynham, Guba, 2013). According to Creswell (2012), the ontological issue relates to the nature of reality and its characteristics. Qualitative researchers embrace the idea of multiple realities and report on these multiple realities by exploring multiple forms of evidence from different individuals' perspectives and experiences. Hence, when studying individuals, I as a qualitative researcher conduct a study with the intent of reporting these multiple realities. Evidence of multiple realities includes the use of multiple forms of evidence in themes using the actual words of different individuals and presenting different perspectives. With the epistemological assumption, as a researcher, I aim to become as close to the people I am studying as possible. The individual perspectives I gathered from the field research are used to compile subjective evidence. Therefore, conducting a qualitative study means that I tried to get as close as possible to the participants being studied collecting subjective evidences assembled based on individual views. Since epistemology is concerned with providing a philosophical grounding for deciding what kinds of knowledge are possible

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Individuals want to comprehend their reality and generate their own unique meanings that correlate to their experiences using Social Constructivism as an interpretative framework for qualitative assumptions (Creswell, 2013). These meanings are not imprinted or innate in each person. Rather, meanings emerge as a result of interactions with others (Creswell, 2013). These meanings are varied and multiple, leading the

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—The study was conducted using a qualitative-inquiry-based phenomenological research design using open-

and how we can ensure that they are both adequate and legitimate, I was able to discover how knowledge is known, through the subjective experiences of people. These are important contexts for understanding what the participants are saying. The longer researchers stay in the field or get to know the participants, the more they know what they know from firsthand information (Guba Lincoln, 2008). Qualitative researchers make their values clear in a study, whereas quantitative researchers bring their values to a study. This is the axiological assumption that qualitative research is based on. In this study, I acknowledged the study's value-laden nature and actively reported their values and prejudices, as well as the value-laden nature of field data (Creswell, 2012). For the Rhetorics, this philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice and uses qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in explaining the experiences and stories of the Filipino teachers working in America amidst the dreadful pandemic.

researcher to look for the complexity of views rather than narrow the meanings into a few categories or ideas. Further, as a researcher, my purpose is to rely as much as possible on the perspectives of the participants. These subjective meanings are frequently disputed in social and historical contexts. In other words, they are developed through interactions with others as well as historical and cultural conventions that work in people's lives, rather than being merely imprinted on them.

ended questions. Phenomenological research is a kind of investigation in which the researcher identifies the essence of participants' descrip-

tions of a phenomenon. The researcher brackets or sets aside his or her own experiences in order to understand the experiences of the study participants (Creswell Creswell, 2017). The researcher was able to produce a description of the school heads' shared meanings with regard to their leadership experiences while emphasizing the similarity of their experiences (Creswell, 2007). Phenomenological approaches are particularly effective at bringing to the fore individual experiences and perceptions from their own points of view, and so challenging structural or normative assumptions. Adding an interpretive component to phenomenological research allows it to inform, support, or question policy and action by allowing it to be utilized as the foundation for practical theory (Lester et al., 2009). As a result, the research methodology is a good fit for capturing the thoughts and experiences of school heads amidst the Covid-19 outbreak. According to Bogart (2017), gaining a clearer image of the occurrence will aid in filling research gaps and providing suggestions for improvement, which in the context of the current study refers to the personal and professional experiences of Filipino teachers working in an international schools in the United States

2.4. Research Participants—This study was conducted in the primary schools of Carlsbad which is a city in and the county seat of Eddy County, New Mexico, United States. As of the 2020 census, the city population was 32,238. Carlsbad is centered at the intersection of U.S. Routes 62/180 and 285, and is the principal city of the Carlsbad-Artesia Metropolitan Statistical Area, which has a total population of 55,435. Located in the southeastern part of New Mexico, Carlsbad straddles the Pecos River and sits at the eastern edge of the Guadalupe Mountains. Carlsbad is a hub for potash mining, petroleum production, and tourism. Only 8 teacher participants served as

of America. The study attempted to present the "living worlds" of the participants, finally exposing their personal relevance in relation to the experience, as a design that captures the experiences of a "chosen few" addressing specific phenomena. Further, this study also employed participants' observations in an In-Depth Interview (IDI). According to Denzel Lincoln (2000), as cited by Lee (2007) in Pelobello (2015), this method involves the use and collection of variety of interviews, observations, history, interactional and visual texts that describe routines, problems and meaning of individual lives. It is an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions that explore a social or human problem. It builds a holistic picture, analyzes words, reports, detailed views of informants, and conducts the study in a natural setting. Furthermore, real life situations need to be explored in terms of their contextual nature as seen by the participants. Therefore, phenomenology is an appropriate and applicable technique to explore the topics on the lived experiences of Filipino teachers working abroad amidst the dreadful pandemic. Common themes will be analyzed, coded and extracted from all of the interviews.

the key informants who were included and were purposely selected based on the nature of their work as OFW teachers and who already experienced at least one year or more teaching in the U.S. The purposive sampling technique, also called judgment sampling, is the deliberate choice of an informant due to the qualities the informant possesses. According to Bernard (2006), it is a non-random technique that does not need underlying theories or a set number of informants. It was the researcher who decided what needs to be known and sets out to find people who can and are willing to provide the information by virtue of knowledge or experience. Purposive sampling is exemplified

through the key informant technique wherein one or a few individuals are solicited to act as guides to the phenomenon. Key informants are observant, reflective members of the community of interest who know much about the topic and are both able and willing to share their knowledge. To gain a variance in perspective from participants, the effort was extended to include both males and females as well as individuals with various levels of educational training, at-

tainment, and rank. Specifically, the inclusion criteria include the following: (1) an OFW with at least one year of experience teaching in New Mexico Schools and who has three years of experience as a teacher in a Philippine School; (2) A Filipino teacher in America who experienced personal and professional challenges working away from the Philippines and (3) a Filipino teacher who experienced teaching in America in the old and new normal.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation The participants were adequately informed about the research undertaking through an informed consent. Consent was given freely and the researcher made sure that the participants understood what was being asked and emphasized that their participations were just purely voluntary. All participants were required to provide written informed consent. The potential participants were approached individually online and given an explanation of the purpose of the study and data collection process. They were also given an appropriate time to ask questions and address concerns. It was explained that their participation was voluntary; they may also refuse to participate or withdraw from the study while it was in progress. When the participants agreed to be part of the In-Depth Interview (IDI), a date, time, and venue were set. Anonymity and Confidentiality The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were preserved by not revealing their names and identity in the data collection, analysis and reporting of the study findings. Privacy and confidentiality of the in-

terview environment were managed carefully during the interview sessions, data analysis and dissemination of the findings. The confidentiality of handling the data is in accordance to Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Interview Sessions Each interview was conducted individual through online. The interview was done with the use of google meet, google sheets and messenger application. The researcher was the only knowledgeable person who can match the identity of the participants in voice and in video recordings. In recording the data, interviews were audio-taped and video recorded with the permission of the participants, and the voice records were transcribed verbatimly. Some notes were taken by the researcher to have genuine, accurate and authentic transcription but the identification of the information of the participants were removed or disguised. Further, the interviews, transcriptions and consent forms were kept in a secured location. To safeguard confidentiality, consent forms were stored in a separate location from the other data so there is no way they can be linked to the interviews.

*2.6. Role of the Researcher—*In qualitative research, the researcher's role is to try to gain access to the needed data while exploring the research participants' ideas and feelings on the phenomenon being studied. This is not a

simple task, to say the least. This entails inviting people to discuss topics that are potentially highly personal to them. Reliving prior experiences might be tough at times when the experiences being explored are somehow negative

to them and are still fresh in the participant's thoughts. My first job as a researcher is to protect participants and their data in any method that data is acquired. Participants shall be given explicit and articulated mechanisms for such safeguarding. Because I am also an immigrant Filipino educator, my job as a researcher is that of an informed inquirer. Prior to conducting this research, I was unaware of the wide uncharted territory of immigrant teacher research. I moved to America years ago and hence have firsthand knowledge of the issue under investigation. Because I was familiar with the procedures involved in working as a foreign teacher, I was able to ask pertinent interview questions.

2.7. Data Collection—In gathering the data, I prepared the interview guide which is composed of three (3) main significant questions which inquired about the experiences of the OFW teachers. A thorough deliberation was made on the aspect of determining the problems of teachers. I made sure that my interview guide was validated by the experts. Moreover, I made sure that all ethical protocols were observed and implemented as I collected the data. An official letter was sent individually to the participants and to Rizal Memorial Colleges asking permission to conduct the study. After receiving the approval letter, the conditions set by the approving authority and the participants will be considered and met. Then, the interview session followed. The interviews were conducted in private areas to protect the confidentiality of the participants. Since the study was conducted during the pandemic - COVID-19, Facebook Messenger, Google Sheets, Zoom, and Google meet were also used for other participants to adhere to the protocols. The interviews were audio recorded with the consent of the participants. In addition, participants were asked to refrain from using names during the interview (names of people and places). At

However, I was not an expert on the distinctive experiences and perspectives of other Filipino teachers. The participants' experiences varied from mine as well. I bracketed or set aside my own immigration experience before gathering data. While some of the facts and experiences were familiar to me, I avoided drawing assumptions about the participants' answers to the interview questions and stayed interested in the research issue. The draft of the manuscript was provided to the participants as part of member checking to verify the rigor and reliability of the findings. No one protested or disagreed with anything the researcher wrote or included in the study.

each interview, I discussed the purpose of the study, the structure of the interview, and the nature, benefits, and risks of participation were discussed with the participants. They were, likewise, informed that participation is voluntary and that all the information gathered are held with strict measures of confidentiality. They were informed that there is no financial compensation for their participation and their participation could raise awareness and provide insight on the phenomenon being investigated. Right after, the transcription of In-depth Interviews (IDI) proceedings was done with the help of the note taker and recorder. I also utilized Inscribe software trial version in transcribing the participants' responses and I also ensured the authentic responses of the informants. In the process, I was able to establish rapport with the interviewees to elicit honest and open responses. After the IDI process, I re-stated or summarized the information, then, presented it to them to vouch for accuracy. The sharing of findings with the participants allows them to critically analyze and comment on it. The participants also affirmed that the summaries presented to them is an original reflection of their views, feelings, and experiences. In this study, their affirmation

of the accuracy and completeness of the information contributed much to the credibility of

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher’s personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. He then finds statements about how individuals were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping, statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information, called “meaning units” or themes. She wrote a description of “what” the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, she wrote a description of “how” the experience happened. This was called “structural description,” and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, he wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the “essence” of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is that it’s a flexible method that can be used both for explorative studies, where the researcher do not have a clear idea of what patterns is being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher know exactly what he or she is interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is that

the study. The data gathered from the IDI were organized accordingly into themes for analysis.

the researcher respects the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analysis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data in order to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it is often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce B., 2018). Triangulation of Data. Triangulation means using more than one method to collect data on the same topic. This is a way of assuring the validity of research through the use of a variety of methods to collect data on the same topic, which involves different types of samples as well as methods of data collection. However, the purpose of triangulation is not necessarily to cross-validate data but rather to capture different dimensions of the same phenomenon (Kulkarni, Prashant, 2013). Environmental triangulation - The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as the time, day, and season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors

are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, then validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—According to Braun and Clark (2006) methods of qualitative data analysis fall in two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) and methods which are situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across a range of different theoretical and epistemological approaches and are therefore very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which through the theoretical freedom “provides flexible and useful research tool, which can potentially provide a rich and detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun and Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my own resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I use several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding on the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay-out and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions ap-

study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement as mentioned was the use of environmental triangulation that best suits the environment of the research being conducted.

propriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved, and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step as data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used a number of different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used forms of thematic grids and charts, the framework technique as develop by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was useful tome in the process of coding, sorting and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedure included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) which consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with coded being the most basic segments of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears interesting; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

(at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, making sure they give the reader immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the

report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes), used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments in relation to the research question.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—For trustworthiness of the study, I adhered to credibility, transferability, confirmability and dependability of qualitative study. Credibility. This is defined as the confidence that can be placed in the truth of the research findings. Credibility establishes whether the research findings represent plausible information drawn from the participants' original data and is a correct interpretation of the participants' original views. One of the key criteria addressed by researchers is that of internal validity, in which they seek to ensure that their study measures or tests what is actually intended. Guba and Lincoln (2009)

argue that ensuring credibility is one of most important factors in establishing trustworthiness. In this study, credibility was considered during the interview process and even in the analysis of data. I made sure that the responses of the participants were transcribed verbatim without adding to or rephrasing their answers. Transferability. The term "transferability" refers to the extent to which the results of one study can be applied to a variety of circumstances (Silverman, 2001). The concern with positivist work is typically establishing that the results of the study at hand can be applied to a larger population. It is impossible to demonstrate that

the findings and conclusions of a qualitative study are relevant to other contexts and populations since qualitative findings are specialized to a small number of specific environments and individuals. Many naturalists feel that even conventional generalizability is impossible in practice since all observations are characterized by the individual situations in which they are made. Dependability. In this study, I used approaches to address the issue of reliability, to demonstrate that comparable results would be reached if the work was redone using the same procedures and circumstances. Guba and Lincoln (2008) emphasize the interconnectedness between credibility and dependability, stating that demonstrating the former goes a long way toward assuring the latter. This can be accom-

plished by combining tactics such as individual interviews to purposively selected different individuals. Confirmability. The qualitative investigator's concept of confirmability and objectivity is a similar concern. In order to lessen the influence of bias, the importance of giving back and sharing the results to the participants in promoting such confirmability was highlighted once more to satisfy this part. The extent to which the researcher confesses his or her own predispositions, according to Miles and Huberman, is a significant factor for confirmability. In the study, part of the steps in analyzing the data were taken to ensure that the conclusions of the study are the result of the informants' experiences and thoughts, rather than my personal ideologies, qualities and preferences.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and their answers based on the responses of the participants of the study. The participants revealed their experiences as they traversed their personal and professional experiences as Filipino teachers working in Public American schools amidst the pandemic. The participants challenges encountered, coping mechanisms and insights were also presented in this part of the research specifically in the primary schools of Carlsbad which is a city in and the county seat of Eddy County, New Mexico, United States. In this chapter, the results of the thematic analysis are presented. It is followed by discussions arranged according to themes and subthemes that were generated.

3.1. Personal and professional experiences of Filipino teachers working in Public American schools amidst the pandemic—In analyzing the lived experiences of the Filipino teachers working in the U.S amidst the pandemic, based on the interview answers shared by the teachers themselves (P1-P6), I was able to identify four major themes. These are Learning through Technology, Technological Stress, More Challenged Teachers and Enhancing Online Educational Practices. The Filipino teachers have expressed different pleasant and unpleasant experiences about their experiences in distance learning but the majority of these ex-

periences are learning-filled scenarios which they believed to be the reasons why they continuously perform their tasks in their schools at present. Majority described Learning amidst the pandemic as related to distance learning or distance education, e-learning, and online learning, which is a kind of education in which teachers and students are physically separated during instruction and various technologies are used to allow student-teacher and student-student communication. The common thing is that distance learning is a safe modality utilized by school individuals in the new normal. This is to continue providing education to the learners amidst these trying times.

3.1.1. *Learning through technology*—It is plausible to argue that a perpetual state of uncertainty has been a prevailing condition, in the Education Sectors in every country. serving as a conduit for the disclosure of this reality. In certain nations, children have already resumed their educational activities, whereas students in other countries are still awaiting the resumption of regular schooling. Certain educational institutions have been deliberating on strategies to effectively prepare for future disruptions. The researchers are currently examining potential investment opportunities that possess attributes of high impact, inclusivity, and sustainability, with the aim of benefiting both educators and students. The integration of digital technologies into the learning process has the potential to bring about significant transformation. However, for this transformation to occur, it is crucial that teachers receive adequate support in understanding how these technologies can be effectively incorporated into pedagogical practices. The inclusion of this requirement poses a challenge for educators, who are already burdened with a crowded curriculum and substantial workload. Digital technology has the potential to disrupt the traditional dynamics between teachers and students, both within the confines of the classroom and beyond. Educators have the ability to employ digital tools as a means of acquainting students with novel information, concepts, and perspectives. Students are provided with a plethora of information and a wide range of perspectives. Currently, educators play a role in aiding students in the development of critical information consumption skills, which could potentially signify a gradual shift from being primarily focused on content expertise to adopting a more comprehensive approach as learning specialists. A learning specialist will support students in understanding, initiating, and processing their own learning, while also engaging in collaborative efforts and collectively constructing knowledge on a global level. As narrated by P2, P3 and P6, expressed the same understanding that Distance Learning a mode of instruction delivery in which learning occurs between a teacher and learners who are geographically distant from one another. When the pandemic emerged and necessitated the transition to remote learning, the teachers adeptly adapted to the new educational landscape while also encountering significant challenges. The educational institution possesses a contemporary curriculum that exhibits a high degree of adaptability, enabling seamless remote implementation. The task presented considerable difficulty at the same time. In response to the viral outbreak, schools implemented novel management techniques and emotional strategies in both the professional and personal capacities to effectively navigate the transition to online teaching. Distance learning plays a pivotal role in providing ongoing education to our learners. Further, Distance learning and remote education are interchangeable terms that refer to the educational approach where students regularly interact with instructors using a range of technological tools, including video conferencing, satellite communication, and internet-based platforms. Distance learning, at its core, pertains to an educational approach where students are geographically separated from their instructors and peers. This suggests that students participate in remote education and lack face-to-face interactions. This pedagogical methodology entails the dissemination of educational content via online platforms or modular resources, enabling learners to engage in the learning process without the continual necessity of being physically present in a conventional school environment. This related to the findings of Cavanaugh (2019) that the pandemic is forcing educators, parents, and students to think critically, problem-solve, be creative, communicate, collaborate and be agile. It is also revealing that there is another way. They said that there is a great moment for learning. All the red tape that keeps things

away is gone and people are looking for solutions that in the past they did not want to see. Students will take ownership over their learning, understanding more about how they learn, what they like, and what support they need. They will personalize their learning, even if the systems around them will not. They believe that genie cannot be put back in the bottle because real change takes place in deep crisis and no one can stop the momentum that will build. But as tech connects people in their homes, its limitations for learning are on display for all the world to see. The crisis has cast a bright light on deep inequalities not just in who has devices and bandwidth, which are critically important, but also who has the skills to self-direct their learning, and whose parents have the time to spend helping. It is a stark reminder of the critical importance of school not just as a place of learning, but of socialization, care and coaching,

3.1.2. Technological Stress—In today's era, Communication technology has become a fundamental component of the exchange of knowledge. Numerous advancements in this discipline have rendered them indispensable for conveying and exchanging knowledge over time. Educators who have primarily received training for in-person instruction encounter difficulties when transitioning to the realm of online teaching. The Covid-19 pandemic and subsequent closure of schools have compelled educators to transition to online platforms in order to facilitate uninterrupted academic progress for students. The process of transitioning to online teaching is inherently challenging, and the achievement of desired outcomes is contingent upon educators possessing the requisite skills, knowledge, and competencies. The impact of technology on education in contemporary times is significant. Educational institutions are anticipated to employ technological tools in order to augment the learning experience of their students; however, obstacles per-

of community and shared space, not things tech has hacked too well (DeBord, 2018). In similar manner, the pandemic is giving tech massive insights at scale as to what human development and learning looks like, allowing it to potentially shift from just content dissemination to augmenting relationships with teachers, personalization, and independence. But the way it has been rolled out, overnight, with no training, and often not sufficient bandwidth, will leave many with a sour taste about the whole exercise. Many people may well continue to associate e-learning with lockdowns, recalling frustrations with trying to log on, or muck When the storm of the pandemic passes, schools may be revolutionized by this experience. Or, they may revert back to what they know. But the world in which they will exist, one marked by rising unemployment and likely recession, will demand more.

taining to its implementation have been recognized. The feasibility of implementing online teaching is contingent upon students and teachers having access to computers and fast internet connections. Another set of factors pertains to teachers themselves, including their attitudes and beliefs regarding the use of technology, as well as their skills and knowledge in this area. If educators have not received adequate training in the field of technology, they may be deficient in the essential competencies required. P1 explained that During this period, both teachers and students engage in numerous adaptations to fulfill expectations, similar to those observed in a traditional classroom environment. Teachers should make an effort to ensure that students are actively involved and intellectually stimulated. However, this can be a challenging task due to the lack of control over technology. Teachers experience technological stress. P2 shared that it is evident that individuals, including foreign educators, encountered challenges in adapting to the novel learning methodolo-

gies implemented during the pandemic. Educators must establish an instructional setting that fosters student engagement and active involvement in the learning process, despite the remote nature of the educational context. P4 added that there were numerous opportunities for professional development that were available at no cost, encompassing both mandatory and optional attendance. The primary emphasis of professional development trainings is predominantly centered on the implementation of online teaching strategies and the enhancement of reading instruction. Teachers should possess proficient computer skills and be adept at utilizing modern applications; otherwise. The abovementioned finding is supported many researchers. The need to make significant changes to curriculum content and delivery were identified as

3.1.3. Enhancing online education practices—Over the past few years, there has been a significant transformation in the concept of traditional education. Due to the widespread adoption of the internet and advancements in technology, the traditional method of acquiring knowledge solely through physical attendance in a classroom setting has become one of several available options for educational pursuits. With the availability of Internet connectivity, individuals are afforded the opportunity to access a high-quality education at their convenience, regardless of time and location. Currently, we find ourselves in a distinct epoch marked by the advent of online education. Online learning, also known as distance education, encompasses the educational process that takes place through the utilization of the Internet. The term commonly used to describe this phenomenon is "e-learning," although it may also be known by alternative designations. Nevertheless, it is important to note that online learning represents just one form of "distance learning," which is a broader concept encompassing any form of learning that takes place outside of a traditional

classroom setting and involves physical separation. The advent of online education has facilitated the ability to engage in studying or teaching activities from any geographical location worldwide. This obviates the necessity of traveling between different places or conforming to a rigid timetable. Furthermore, apart from the temporal benefits, there is also a financial advantage to consider, as the saved funds can be reallocated towards alternative areas of focus. The participants of the study reiterated the notion that online education is currently the most efficacious method of instruction and knowledge acquisition. P4 shared that as an educator currently faced with the task of teaching online, her pedagogical approach entails prioritizing experiential learning for students, even within the virtual environment. The incorporation of interactive activities remains a crucial component in educational settings, even within the context of distance learning. It is imperative to recognize that the dynamic between teachers and students continues to foster meaningful interactions. P5 expressed that the training, experience, and passion of a teacher are crucial factors in en-

abling them to effectively navigate challenging circumstances that may arise. Irrespective of geographical location, temporal context, or the individuals we interact with, the utilization of technology remains a viable means to enhance and refine our practices. The statements of the participants were supported by the notions that the quality of children's online experiences can differ depending on the support provided, as described in a sociocultural framework. Children can learn the benefits from observing a diverse range of technologies. Guided interactions can support children to acquire knowledge and skills, and develop positive dispositions about distance education. How teachers enhance children's encounters with technologies through guided interactions is a key consideration to support children's engagement with online learning as emphasized by Plowman and McPake (2013). Early childhood teachers' efficacy in using technology is another issue in the effectiveness of distance education. The attitudes and skills of early childhood teachers in the use of technology also affect children's motivation and learning. Early childhood teachers often use technologies in their teaching, but usually as teaching tools to show pictures or videos. They need to take on additional roles if they are to teach online (Kalogiannakis 2010).

3.1.4. More challenged teachers—In analyzing the challenges encountered by the Filipino teachers teaching abroad amidst the pandemic, based on the interview answers shared by the teachers themselves, I was able to identify three subthemes for the challenges they faced: Intermittent Internet Connections, Lack of physical activity and interactions and Language Barriers Online. These problems are the common themes gathered when asked about the problem and difficulties they experienced on the phenomenon under study.

3.1.5. Intermittent Internet Connections—Teachers cited poor internet connectivity as one of the major challenges in their online distance

learning activities. Students who do not have access to the internet are unable to communicate with their teachers or classmates, conduct independent research, or receive online assistance with their schoolwork. If a household does not have access to the internet, they may be unable to obtain some pieces of information or maintain an open line of communication with their children's schools and teachers. Students who do not have access to the internet at home are unable to do their homework, which is one of the most significant challenges they encounter. The practice of assigning homework has, for a very long time, been the subject of heated discussion within the field of education. Pupils who originate from households with a low income and students who are members of a minority are frequently already at a disadvantage. The so-called accomplishment gap will only widen if people aren't provided with consistent access to high-speed internet. Pupils from families with lower incomes and students from underrepresented minority groups may now also be forced to compete with their peers who do not have access to the internet. This new imbalance is frequently referred to as the digital divide, and it is a problem that is becoming increasingly prevalent in education. Families living on a low income can have access to the internet through the assistance of several programs that are funded by the government and other organizations. There are still millions of students who do not have access to the internet, despite the fact that some progress has been made in closing the digital divide.

3.1.6. Lack of Physical Activity and Interactions—In a typical face-to-face classroom, participants interact with the instructor by asking questions, expressing concerns, and requesting clarifications; however, in an online class, interactions are limited. Participation of learners is the incorporation of opportunities for audiences, such as students, to interact and be heard throughout an event or online activity. Interac-

tions between classmates are also problematic in distance learning. The lack of environmental control is one of the most significant disadvantages of technology-based learning, particularly when one considers that a presenter has near-total control over the components in a live setting. Sitting alone in vacant classrooms while conversing with a screen full of faces, sometimes juggling two or more laptops and phones, an additional keyboard, and other technologies that teachers mastered overnight, teachers today appear to be busier than in the past. On a daily basis, however, distance education feels marginally more challenging. As the pandemic spreads this time, an increasing number of schools are reopening with hybrid models, prompting many instructors to modify their schedules and curricula to accommodate both in-person and remote instruction, such as attending online classes. This is one of the numerous obstacles faced by the study's participants. It is well known that when people cannot physically move around, particularly learners, they become readily fatigued and lose motivation to learn. P4 shared that students are restricted in how much they can physically move around when they are attending an online lesson. Their interactions are limited, which is also true for the aspect of being an online instructor where you communicate with students. P5 expressed the lack of face-to-face interaction that she was able to have with students and their guardians is one of the challenges she had when teaching students through distance education. Since was unable to physically interact with or instruct her students, their education may take a very different form than she had anticipated at this point in time. P6 explained that maintaining adherence to the fundamental principles that underpin both teaching and learning presents a challenge for him. Whether he enjoyed it or not, he will be forced to go back to the job as a teacher since he had no other option. It was impossible for him to determine whether or not his students

are actually gaining knowledge because, in contrast to traditional classes, they do not usually participate in various activities. This is related to the notions of Numerous publications that acknowledged the concerns about youngsters' safety amid extended school closures and home confinement (Dorn et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020). These factors included a lack of physical activity, increased screen time, and unhealthy diets. Additional psychological impacts of quarantine have been studied previously, including the stress caused by fear of infection, boredom, frustration, and a loss of socializing with peers and teachers. While students were quarantined in their homes, they encountered additional factors that may jeopardize their well-being. Insufficient personal space and, for many, financial loss in the family contributed to anxiety and despair (Wang et al., 2020). Brooks et al. (2020) stated that feelings of loss, perplexity, rage, and insomnia are frequent throughout extended periods of time apart from others. In the spring of 2020 in U.S, students and instructors alike were quarantined.

3.1.7. Language Barriers Online—The term "language barriers" refers to the challenges encountered by individuals in terms of linguistic communication, as well as the strategies used to overcome these obstacles. Effective communication plays a crucial role in fostering a dynamic and productive work environment because it promotes mutual understanding and efficiency. The presence of communication barriers between two parties has the potential to impede constructive dialogue and increase the probability of misunderstandings. It is anticipated that collaborating with the locals will present challenges when engaging in pedagogical activities at an international educational institution located in China. The participants had difficulty acclimating to their unfamiliar work environment, establishing effective communication with colleagues, understanding their colleagues' points of view, and communicating with indi-

viduals across the educational institution even through online. This statement pertains to the research findings that highlight the significance of both linguistic and paralinguistic elements, such as body language, gestures, and facial expressions, in facilitating effective communication in the context of multicultural issues (Byram et al., 2009). Consequently, instances of miscommunication may arise within the educational setting or in engagements with individuals from the local community. Despite the fact that international teachers have amassed a considerable body of language proficiency in the target language, it may not suffice for facilitating effective communication. The efficacy of communication can be impeded by a diverse range of factors such as novel accents, dialects, id-

iomatic expressions, pauses, spelling variations, and nonverbal cues (Ephratt, 2011; Mancini-Cross et al., 2009). Moreover, both native and non-native English instructors exhibited a lack of ability to effectively connect their instructional methodologies with their international students in practical contexts. According to Ulla (2018), educators encounter various challenges in facilitating their students' learning, including limited exposure to the English language, an absence of a well-defined English curriculum, inadequate teacher preparation, and a dearth of motivation towards English language acquisition. According to Altun (2015), educators who are employed in foreign countries encounter diverse curricula that deviate from their own.

3.2. The Coping Mechanisms of teachers amidst the pandemic in Public American Schools—The second research objective of this study focuses on the coping mechanisms of Filipino teachers on the challenges they experienced in working in American school while also implementing distance learning. Figure four shows

the summary of their coping strategies. As seen in Figure 4, the coping strategies of the participants are divided into two major themes. These are Considering professional development and Valuing Resilience and Change Management. These summarized the coping strategies of the teachers as they deal with the challenges of the current research circumstances.

3.2.1. Considering Professional Development—The present study examines the concept of self-development for educators as a continuous process that entails a critical evaluation of one's own performance, including an assessment of strengths and areas requiring improvement. Subsequently, educators develop a personalized approach to implement and evaluate enhancements in the identified areas. The recognition of the wide-ranging influence of social, economic, and technological advancements on the teaching profession is well-established. Therefore, it is crucial for educators to view their profession as a continuous learning process in order to stay updated with the ever-changing

and evolving educational environment. This implies that educators are consistently presented with opportunities for personal and professional growth, as there is always a skill to enhance or a pedagogical challenge to overcome. The participants maintained the conviction that, in order to adeptly navigate the challenges inherent in working in a foreign nation, they perceive this experience as a chance for continual personal and professional development. The participants of this study presented their ideas as to how they coped with some difficulties or challenges they experienced. Participant 2 to 4 expressed the same ideas. P2 Participated in online training sessions and accessing pre-recorded video sem-

Fig. 3. Personal and professional experiences of Filipino teachers working in Public American schools amidst the pandemic

inars for professional development. P3 narrated that the adequate attention to the well-being of both teachers and students is imperative for schools, as the provision of excellent teaching and learning alone is insufficient. Access to technology is a prerequisite, albeit insufficient, for effective educational practices. It is imperative that educators receive timely and comprehensive training in digital pedagogy to enhance their proficiency in utilizing technological tools. Consequently, I actively seek out opportunities to acquire knowledge and enhance my digital skills. Additionally, P4 shared that she has chosen to enroll in additional courses to enhance her comprehension of the legal statutes applicable in this jurisdiction. Additionally, she decided to undertake Spanish language classes in order to facilitate communication with my monolingual students and parents to a certain extent. In summary, the objective is to consistently advance one's professional development. Without a doubt, the opportunity to work overseas has consistently demonstrated its benefits for educators in terms of their personal and professional growth, despite the challenges faced by some individuals. Altun (2015) argues that participating in international experiences has multiple

3.2.2. Valuing Resilience and Change Management—Educators who opt to engage in international teaching assignments and explore educational institutions and lifestyles in diverse settings undoubtedly challenge themselves to the utmost extent. Engaging in risk-taking behavior within personal and professional domains. The aforementioned decision serves as evidence for the necessity of resilience within the field of education. The profession of teaching is widely regarded as highly gratifying and personally enriching; however, embarking on a career in teaching necessitates a substantial amount of dedication and resilience. The presence of teacher autonomy contributes to the in-

benefits for instructors. Firstly, it helps them develop cultural awareness, which in turn allows them to establish positive connections with students from diverse backgrounds. Additionally, engaging in international experiences also helps instructors refine their teaching methodologies, making them more effective in the classroom. One of the key benefits associated with international experience lies in the acquisition of knowledge pertaining to diverse cultures and the comprehension of individuals' lives from a multitude of countries. This knowledge provides individuals with an enhanced understanding of the distinct needs of students from diverse cultural backgrounds, enabling them to effectively deliver education by customizing it to address these particular requirements. To ensure successful education of students from diverse cultural backgrounds, it is crucial for teachers to possess a thorough comprehension of the values and beliefs held by these individuals (De Villar Jiang, 2012). The adoption of a standardized curriculum and instructional approaches especially in technology utilization is likely to be widely accepted by a heterogeneous student body.

herent dynamism, intrigue, and adaptability of the teaching profession. Each day presents a chance to motivate, involve, and establish connections with enthusiastic students who possess a plethora of abilities, ambitions, and concepts. Nevertheless, the study participants reported the situations in reverse chronological order. According to the participants, teaching abroad necessitates fortitude and bravery as a result of the persistent existence of uncertainty. The concept of "resilience" was cited by a majority of the participants when asked about their most significant international learning experience. When queried about recommendations for individuals aspiring to become international educators, a re-

curing theme that surfaced was the imperative of cultivating resilience and managing change in response to the unpredictable nature of existence. Additionally, the local community of Filipino individuals provides support in the region. The role of an individual's faith, specifically their religious beliefs, is a significant determinant in motivating and propelling their actions. The positive attitude and cheerfulness exhibited by Filipinos in various circumstances contribute significantly to their coping mechanisms. Additionally, local teachers demonstrate a high level of support, often displaying a welcoming and approachable demeanor. P6 explained that Filipinos exhibit remarkable adaptability and resilience. Teachers possess a greater capacity for adaptability to change, confidence, appreciation, and open-mindedness. This can be attributed to the extensive training teachers have received, their participation in international conventions, and their interactions with a multitude of experienced educators. Numerous scholastic studies have examined the difficulties educators confront when instructing in foreign countries, and this finding is related to those studies. Miller (2018) investigated the strategies used by teachers who received training abroad to navigate their professional responsibilities and teaching encounters in England, compared to their teaching experiences in their home countries. The findings indicate that foreign-trained instructors are able to meet the demands of their profession, although they may not experience significant

success in some areas. In a study conducted by Roy and Lavery (2017), the experiences of educators who received their training outside of Australia prior to their employment in a public secondary school setting in the country were investigated. Prior to securing employment in the field of education, the researchers wanted to investigate the obstacles and difficulties faced by instructors. Their research revealed a dearth of information regarding post-immigration life, the dangers associated with misinformation, delays in the registration process, inconsistencies in English language proficiency requirements, and difficult living conditions in rural areas, among others. Nevertheless, despite these obstacles, the instructors demonstrated resilience and fulfilled their contractual obligations abroad. The focus of Mizzi's (2017) study was to investigate the experiences of visiting professors in post-secondary educational institutions. The study's findings indicated that being a visiting professor provides individuals with a valuable opportunity to enhance their intercultural competence and professional practice. On the basis of the findings, the provision of a preparatory pedagogy has the potential to assist faculty members in exploring the various challenges and benefits associated with teaching or conducting research abroad. Unquestionably, operating in a foreign country necessitates fortitude and resiliency, which is consistent with the findings of the aforementioned scholarly works, as the participants in the study also faced these obstacles.

3.3. Educational Management Insights and Lessons Learned of Filipino teachers regarding their experiences as foreign teachers in Public American Schools—The last research objective of this study focuses on the insights or lessons learned by the Filipino teachers regarding their experiences as foreign teachers in Public American Schools. Figure five shows the summary of insights and lessons learned.

Based on the experiences and challenges of the teachers in public American schools, the participants of this study had their respective insights to further improve their experiences abroad and in educational implementations. These insights were some of the personal thoughts of the participants that they deemed significant in understanding their real situations in the new normal. As seen in Figure 5, the insights of the

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanisms of teachers amidst the pandemic in Public American Schools

participants are divided into two major themes. These are: Value of Social Connectedness and the importance of adaptation for survival. These summarized the insights of the teachers based on their experiences in schools including the challenges and coping mechanisms. Based on

their responses, although they experienced ups and downs in the process, still their insights have always reminded them on the lessons and things that they learned which made them more equipped and competent as Teachers working amidst the pandemic.

3.3.1. Value of Social Connectedness— The abrupt transition to remote learning immediately tested the teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and skills. Previously 'nice-to-have' skills in digital integration became 'must-haves,' traditional classroom management and instructional design methodologies were no longer applicable, and everyone was compelled to develop a high level of comfort with uncertainty as weekly standards and expectations changed. And as the new face of education approaches and the global pandemic persists, educators were bracing for these abrupt and temporary shifts by implementing distance learning and recognizing the value of being connected during these difficult times. School connectedness is the extent to which children feel individually embraced, respected, included, and supported by others in the school social environment, and for the participants, this is of utmost importance during the pandemic. The participants of this study had given their respective insights as to how they felt about all their experiences and how American Schools better the distance learning practices. P4 shared that when endeavoring to improve online instruction, it is crucial to consider the various facets of both positive and negative feedback. When students, teachers, and other stakeholders are interconnected, the resolution of problems becomes more manageable. P5 expressed that by conducting online instruction or utilizing online technologies presents challenges due to the unreliable internet connection. When devising strategies to maintain academic engagement and enhance knowledge retention among students or learners, it is important to

take into account the support and input from diverse sources, including individuals. In order to ensure the educational advancement of the students, it is imperative that all individuals maintain a connection. P6 added that teaching in the current era presents several challenges; however, by establishing and nurturing robust relationships with various educational institutions and relevant parties, educators can effectively surmount any impediments they encounter. These findings are related to the notions that the early years is central for young children to move from more egocentric, independent play to engaging and connecting with peers. Therefore, building opportunities to continue to develop social connectedness is important during this period of social isolation. Singh and Thrman (2019) says online platforms, such as Google Classroom or Zoom, provide opportunities for whole class interaction and also break out rooms. Break-out rooms can be used for both formal group tasks and informal conversations and both are important. For those students who do not feel comfortable talking in a class or group forum and would rather type their interaction, chat forums can be made available on some platforms. Allowing children to work on the same documents through Google Docs, meanwhile, can be used to promote connectedness and a shared goal. They added that it is important to continue social connectedness within classes and across year levels through online platforms, by post and by phone. Further, Wedenoja (2016) also added two more suggestions include engagement in secure online games, allowing for fun interaction while being mindful of security and

adult supervision and setting learning tasks that engage children in interviewing or seeking information from family and friends, helping them

keep connected with significant others outside of their class peers.

3.3.2. Importance of adaptation for survival—It is advisable to anticipate unforeseen circumstances. This recommendation offers the most advantageous guidance for individuals who are considering relocating to a foreign country. Educators engage in meticulous preparations, especially when undertaking teaching assignments in international contexts. There exists the potential for the individual to have attained a high level of competence in the native language and acquired certification in Teaching as a Foreign Language. Nevertheless, it is crucial to acknowledge that there are frequently supplementary factors that necessitate careful examination beyond initial assessments. The experience of adapting to a foreign classroom environment can be intellectually stimulating, especially when confronted with unanticipated and nuanced obstacles. Nevertheless, it is important to note that the individuals involved in this study place significant emphasis on the acquisition of valuable insights through the process of survival and adaptation. Change can be seen as a tangible expression of growth. Periods of transition punctuate our lives. Despite the prevalent aversion to change among individuals, adopting a proactive stance towards new opportunities and cultivating an optimistic mindset can lead to remarkable accomplishments. Filipino educators have encountered significant transformations and challenges in their professional journey. The participants may have found these significant life changes to be overwhelming; however, they made the conscious decision to embrace the new opportunities and seize the chance to survive and adapt. The experience has had a positive impact on me as it has fostered an increased sense of self-trust. P5 added that the training, experience, and passion of a teacher

are crucial factors in enabling them to effectively navigate challenging circumstances that may arise. Irrespective of location, temporal context, or individuals encountered, the utilization of technology remains a viable means to enhance and refine our practices. P6 expressed that an individual has developed the capacity to effectively participate in conflicts by striking a balance between asserting their own stance and being receptive to adjustments and guidance from individuals with greater expertise. This approach is undertaken with the objective of fostering personal and professional development. This finding is related to the grounded theory of goal-attitude-adaptation, which can be perceived as a crucial factor in the endurance of Filipino teachers abroad. This theory upholds the notion that successful adaptation and survival necessitate the presence of well-defined goals and a positive attitude. The findings of the study shed light on the experiences of millennial educators as they engage in the endeavor of teaching abroad in order to attain personal and professional development. The inevitability of change necessitates a comprehensive understanding of its significance, thereby highlighting the importance of various teaching and learning concepts in contemporary times. In the study conducted by de Mesa and de Guzman in 2006, it was suggested that teachers should undergo a process of re-socialization to effectively fulfill their new responsibilities, thereby enabling students to assume more active roles in teaching and learning activities. Moreover, it is believed that specific deficiencies in one's life, stemming from a state of deprivation, can serve as motivators for individuals when left unfulfilled. In reality, individuals possess an inherent inclination to achieve their utmost capabilities regardless

Fig. 5. Insights and Lessons Learned of Filipino teachers regarding their experiences as foreign teachers in Public American Schools

of the situation, and their determination to meet these demands intensifies as the duration of deprivation prolongs. This can be observed in the context of hunger, where the longer an individual goes without food, the more pronounced their appetite becomes. According to Maslow (1943, as cited in McLeod, 2018), it is necessary for individuals to fulfill their lower-level deficit needs before progressing to higher-level growth needs. However, he later emphasized that the fulfillment of human desires is not a binary event, but rather a nuanced process. The previous statements made by the individual may have given rise to the erroneous notion that a requirement must be entirely fulfilled prior to the manifestation of a subsequent human longing.

The motivation for individuals to have growth needs stems from their desire to enhance their personal development, rather than from any perceived deficiencies. If the individual's growth needs are sufficiently fulfilled, they may achieve the highest level of self-actualization (McLeod, 2018). Indeed, the act of traveling to foreign countries serves as a catalyst for fostering self-awareness, personal growth, and advancements in the realms of survival and adaptability. According to Serin (2017), individuals who have engaged in international travel possess a heightened understanding of political dynamics and social dynamics, in addition to a greater ability to cultivate personal development, when compared to those who have not traveled abroad.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study is presented, from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the experiences, challenges encountered, coping mechanisms and insights of public elementary school teachers about teaching amidst the pandemic specifically in the primary schools of Carlsbad which is a city in and the county seat of Eddy County, New Mexico, United States. To achieve the research objectives, I made use of a qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis. In adherence to Cresswell's (2006) guidelines in which open-ended questions for interviews were applied to get an authentic understanding of people's experiences. Furthermore, through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their own definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored which were the experiences of Filipino teachers as teaching the U.S and in the implementation of distance learning.

4.1. Findings—Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the teacher participants, the following themes were revealed. The lived experiences of Filipino teachers on teaching amidst the pandemic and on distance education revealed the following themes: Learning through Technology, Technological Stress, More Challenged Teachers and Enhancing Online Educational Practices. There were three subthemes that emerged on the chal-

lenges experienced by the participants. These are Intermittent Internet Connections, Lack of physical activity and interactions and Language Barriers Online. The coping mechanisms of teacher participants on the challenges they experienced were: Considering professional development and Valuing Resilience and Change Management. The educational management insights drawn from the participants were the Value of Social Connectedness and the importance of adaptation for survival

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. As a result of the COVID-19 / Coronavirus pandemic, the full impact of school closures and the shift to distance learning on teachers will never be totally known for now. We can only do our best to learn about and comprehend the experiences of educators at this time especially those who are teaching abroad. Learning via Technology, Technological Stress, More Challenged Teachers, and Enhancing Online Educational Practices were some of the themes that emerged from the lived experiences of Filipino teachers on teaching in the middle of the pandemic and on distance education. Teachers considered Technology as the most important factor in teaching-learning processes at present. Providing More Educational Materials can make the

students more abreast with the latest demand for learning and may enhance their achievement and learning. Learning Online has become more than a challenge for Teachers in schools. The issues that were faced by the participants may be broken down into three distinct subthemes that arose. These include irregular Internet connections, an insufficient amount of physical activity and social engagement, and difficulties communicating verbally over the internet. Teachers' challenges are doubled this time. The intermittent Internet connections which is a channel for teaching and learning pose negative experiences to the teachers. Teachers' worry about the Lack of physical activity and interactions that causes academic achievement gaps among the learners. The competencies set by the Education Department are not really mastered by

the learners. Although extremely challenging, Distance education was also Convenient for the teachers. Taking into account opportunities for professional growth and placing a high value on resilience and adaptability were two of the coping strategies that participating teachers employed in response to the difficulties they had encountered in their careers abroad. To effectively mitigate the existing deficiencies, Filipino educators adopt coping mechanisms that consist of two fundamental components: continuous self-enhancement and the development of resilience. Providing teachers with customized training programs that address the specific challenges they face has proven to be advantageous. Language barriers, particularly among peers and students, pose significant challenges. The process of adjusting to a new and unfamiliar work setting can frequently pose difficulties, involving various personal and professional hurdles for educators in question. Filipino educators are mandated to familiarize themselves with the differences and difficulties involved in adapting to the cultures and environments of their host nations. The participants maintain the perspective that involvement in professional pursuits within a global setting fosters continuous personal growth. The primary aim of the individual is to consistently acquire knowledge. In spite of the presence of external pressures, individuals possess the capacity to attain a state of harmonious equilibrium wherein they effectively balance the various demands of life with the pursuit of personal enjoyment. This is accomplished through the manifestation of resilience in their daily pursuits. The insights shared by the participants in the field of educational management centered on the pivotal role played by resilience and adaptability, and the importance of personal growth and development. Having a comprehension of cultural differences is crucial. The existence of diverse multicultural education environments and their corresponding profes-

sional contexts contributes to the possibility of a deeper understanding of different cultures and promotes the principle of equality. This discourse supports the notion of Filipino educators engaging in voluntary self-improvement, while also encouraging them to cultivate a heightened level of tolerance towards the multifaceted elements that constitute their professional milieu. There exist multiple rationales for their continued adoption of enhanced opportunities. Despite facing various obstacles, the individuals under consideration acquired a heightened comprehension of the significance of resilience when confronted with uncertainties. The recognition of environmental stress among educators in the Philippines has been acknowledged. This mitigates the situation, however, when employees are able to discover purpose and significance in their occupation. Teachers desire growth and relevance because they care about their students. They Value Social Connections where teachers learned that they must be Self-Adaptable toward change. As teachers advance in their careers, they develop as individuals who contribute not just to the education of children but also to the development of every nation. Their drive to develop and connect with others professionally and personally extends beyond their classroom needs and interests. It is their determination to overcome all obstacles in order to become agents of social transformation by improving as students and teachers. The findings of this study shed light on the various experiences of Filipino teachers working abroad amidst the pandemic. The study looked into the educators' actions and reactions. These experiences, acquired through systematic interviews, can help other educators interested in the phenomenon under study, as well as other scholars pursuing comparable lines of study. Participants' coping techniques can be used as a resource for those who find themselves in a similar position.

4.3. *Future Directions*—Based on the findings of the study, it is important that the findings are properly relayed and used by the significant people whom this research was intended for. The American School administrators and heads may craft teacher enhancement programs in implementing distance education in schools through webinars or face-to-face training where online interactions and a positive social presence should be acknowledged as an important design feature in the creation of professional development programs. They have to make all distance education programs more inclusive or integrative with proper planning and implementation strategies rather than just implementing distance education without proper guidelines and programs. They may consider teachers' internet connection needs, workloads, and resources to successfully provide an effective professional development program. The educational institutions where Filipino teachers may be employed may assign senior teachers with valuable support networks to newly employed Filipino teachers. This support can be provided in a variety of ways, such as through training programs or mentoring relationships that include academic, technological, cultural, and institutional-specific information. Educators may also be advised to cultivate positive relationships with their colleagues and members of the local community, which includes both their immediate school community and people they meet outside of the school. Educators who engage with a new culture in a receptive and inquisitive manner have the opportunity to effectively model intercultural attitudes and cultivate a positive view of the cultures from which they originate. In addition to the potential for personal gain, they also have the ability to contribute to the improvement of their educational institution and the global communities in which they operate. Multiple facets of the individual's experiences in foreign environments demonstrate his or her cultural adaptability. The aforementioned factors have a significant impact on the emotional health, sense of belonging, and sense of purpose of individuals, as well as their ongoing commitment to advancing the field of education on a global scale and the well-being of those they collaborate with. The policy makers or the government especially those who have the power or authority to create educational mandates, policy actions and orders to craft guidelines in providing uninterrupted and low-cost internet facilities for the smooth conduct of online education. Additional gadgets for the teachers and students may also be procured and may be freely be given to them since the teachers in the study utilized their own resources in purchasing updated gadgets intended for their classes. Further, as emphasized, providing more educational materials can make the students more abreast with the latest demand for learning and may enhance their achievement and learning. The future researchers may embark on the same research with different participants, place and school. Other avenues not scrutinized in this research may also be explored.

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